

Design and Selection of the Nanoaerobic Vertical Bioreactor (NVBS)[®] System for wastewater treatment: Innovative and sustainable vision

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Designing and selecting a wastewater treatment system is not a matter of filling in boxes in software, as it depends on extensive applied knowledge and sensitivity of reaction kinetics and technical criteria. A comprehensive decision must be based on complex data analysis and NVBS[®] impresses with its unique characteristics that make it an innovative and sustainable solution to projects, with the required flexibility and scalability with the best cost-benefit.

Summary:

This simple longitudinal qualitative analysis presents the widespread use of information technology in the modeling of wastewater treatment plants, whose future impact challenges have not yet been identified, and compares with NVBS[®] systems. Stoichiometric data quality defines the eligibility criteria for a wastewater treatment process. The technical criteria determine the sustainability of the project. Failure to take into account the importance of this information is critical to the efficiency of the processing used, casting doubt on the proper use of computer models. NVBS[®] is developed with the appropriate control of the variables in their smallest details, established in a strategic modeling of the chemical, biochemical and biological reactions of the microbial metabolic pathways within a dynamic and flexible process that gives the user the efficiency of removing the pollutant load without the production of sludge and greenhouse gases.

Keywords:

Stoichiometry, Technical criteria, Wastewater Treatment, Nanoaerobic Vertical Bioreactor System (NVBS[®]), WWT Technology

1. Definition and Selection of a Wastewater Treatment Model:

For decades, wastewater treatment projects were determined based on models defined in sanitation engineering textbooks and based on calculations taught and repeated exhaustively in universities. The system was selected through the expertise of the designer and, when modifications occurred during the operation, the results were discouraging, impacting that water contamination continued to rise uncontrollably, not only due to the lack of sanitation, but also due to the inefficiency of the existing systems.

In recent decades, however, with the great progress of information technology, applications and software have been developed to model the design of wastewater treatment systems, expanding the range of options so that more professionals and any user, without being an expert in sanitation, can perform optimization, simulation and engineering. Re-engineering or synthesizing a wastewater treatment system, offering the speed of the computer process. This new capability made it possible to consider a greater number of variables when evaluating the impact of decisions in a short time, reducing, in theory, trial-and-error costs of traditional design.

Basically, the kinetic models of these software allow the developer to have a wide range of options for selecting the wastewater treatment process, based on predictions and trends. The software templates must be fed and **the efficiency of the design will be based on the quality of the STOICHIOMETRIC DATA and TECHNICAL CRITERIA** that are used in the modeling process, as well as the individual calibration and validation processes of the software in each specific project. The data feed must be **dynamic** throughout the execution of the project and **the flexibility** of the designs are part of the applicability of the technique.

Although these tools facilitate decision-making to define that the model to be used will be functional, it should be noted that the results now depend on greater **responsibility in the acquisition of real data**, otherwise the operational problems will remain the same or worse than traditional techniques.

Stoichiometry process is like a recipe for making chocolate chip cookies: It shows which reactants (the ingredients) combine to form which products (the cookies), as well as their quantities and numerical relationships between the reactants and the products (such as how many cups of flour are needed to make a group of cookies) (Kotz, 2008).

The technical criteria, in turn, are what determine if the tools (bowl, spoon, mixer, etc.) that will be used for the mixing of these ingredients, and the process of reactions (cooking, baking, frying, etc.) will work properly according to the design:

TECHNICAL CRITERIA (*)	IMPORTANCE
1. Applicability of the process	Determine if the required reactions occur with the selected reactants within the chosen model.
2. Applicability to the required flow rate	Limits the volume of reagents that will enter the model.
3. Applicability to Flow Variation	Indicates volumetric reagent safety margins for required reactions.
4. Characteristics of the residual influent	Details which reagents are present and which need to be added.
5. Inhibitors and non-reactive constituents	Predicts whether items that affect reactions can enter the system .
6. Climatic constraints (rainfall regime, temperature, soil stability)	Forecasts impacts that will modify the usual characteristics of expected reactions.
7. Reaction Kinetics and Reactor Selection	INTEGRATE the reagents, reactions, volumes, affectations and impacts to obtain a calculated result = STISCHIMETRY .
8. Performance	Determine the efficiency of the expected outcome.
9. Waste Treatment	Indicates the products of the expected reactions.
10. Sludge Processing	Calculates the expected product volume and determines additional processes for stabilization, handling, and disposal.
11. Regulatory Environmental Restrictions	Set the rules that must be followed.
12. Chemical Requirement	Indicates if additional reagents are needed .
13. Energy Requirements	Establishes the energy balance of the process.
14. Staffing Requirements	It predicts the quantity and quality of human resources for the execution and operation of the system.
15. Operation and Maintenance Requirements	Determine the sustainability of the project.
16. Area Availability	Look at geographic location data, population growth, future implications.
17. Other Requirements	Climate Change is a reality and the generation of GHG must be observed with caution in the definition of systems since they may generate limitations in the near future.

(*) Defined in Metcalf & Eddy, 5a. Edition, "Wastewater Engineering: Treatment and Resource Recovery"

1. Modeling Challenges

The hasty and massive use of modeling software is creating new failures in the global sanitation process, as the quality of efficiency of the design is not being respected. Companies in the sanitation area hide under

the premise of using information technology and introduce superficial projects without any stoichiometric basis or compliance with technical criteria. Just as a doctor requires years of clinical practice to develop his diagnostic capacity and propose a treatment, which is why he cannot be replaced by software; In the definition of design and selection of wastewater treatment model, the same scoop should be respected.

Our review of the various projects¹ for more than 50 thousand inhabitants executed in the Latin American region in the last 15 years observe as a common characteristic that the stoichiometric data used in the calculation memory correspond only to 5 reagent parameters (BOD5, COD, SS, N and P) of a simple punctual sample and without traceability in the documents; as well as in the technical criteria the socio-economic reality of the areas are not considered of execution, raised enormous doubts whether in the decision-making of the final design they have really considered the typical characteristics of operation and maintenance: electricity consumption, availability of inputs, handling and disposal of sludge.

In the region there are several wastewater treatment concessions, in which large treatment plants were built, which do not comply with the treatment requirements and have led to legal attacks without a technical context to support it.

By drawing a methodology for the analysis of the possible causes of model inefficiency, we begin to enumerate the fact that the software presents a factory default model in which the design delivered is STEADY STATE, that is, it imitates the performance of a plant on a long-term scale, ignoring sudden disturbances in the process (Vanrolleghem, et al. 2003). These models use **averaged data** that is not time-dependent, does not describe the hydraulic details of the plant, **and assumes a constant inlet flow and concentrations**.

In addition, Nutt et al., 2004, indicate that the main benefit of using modeling as software is to allow the operator to make changes during the applicability of the model in order to anticipate requirements when one or another process has special circumstances whose intervention must occur before the treatment plant is built.

The revised reality shows that no calculation memory has been calibrated and validated, that is, modified from its default version; or that after the initial modeling, changes have been made aimed at the specific requirements of the projects presented, due to the very nature of flexible modeling of the software used. Our technical opinion assesses that at least the criteria established in the health literature (climatic criteria, environmental restrictions, personnel requirements, among others) were not considered for selection and design for an efficient execution of the project or a design reevaluation.

We observed kinetic definitions of treatment in basic processes of Primary Settling> Biological Reactor> Secondary Settling in most of the systems evaluated, a model whose use dates back to the early 1950s and presents multiple widely recognized shortcomings. Thus, we question the effectiveness of the application of modeling software or whether the professionals who are using it know how to apply it and evaluate its results.

The current wastewater treatment market has modernized treatment techniques, such as the use of special filtrations, suspended biofilms, aeration in nano bubbles and the results delivered by the softwares do not reflect this evolution, most likely because it is not being handled by sanitation experts.

Possible Causes of Modeling Inefficiency

Cause	Impact
Low quality of stoichiometric data	It does not allow the software to robustly predict design requirements and define an appropriate process.
Use of Steady State Software	It does not recognize variabilities in the selected process as it uses average and constant data.
Failure to make changes to the process	There is no validation of the data used and it does not meet the requirements of the specific project
Definitions of Basic Kinetics	The selected treatment techniques have known operational problems that were not taken into account. Modern technologies are not used as a solution option.
Human resource for software management	It doesn't feed the software with the information required to get a proper result. They don't do the software calibration and validation. They do not make operational modifications during the execution of the project.

¹ These projects can be located on public procurement websites in the Republic of Panama, Costa Rica, Colombia, Mexico and Brazil; They can also be traced on the websites of financing banks in the region. We reserve the right to specifically mention their names because we do not have authorization.

1. NVBS® System

The Vertical Nanoaerobic Bioreactor System (NVBS)® is a biological wastewater treatment system that was designed and developed observing the optimal efficiency of biological removal of the pollutant load from a liquid effluent; where it is modeled, calculated, and designed to create the specific environment for the activities of bacterial biochemical processes.

Unlike existing engineering models, which are based on process hydraulics and sludge generation, the NVBS® System is the application of BIOTECHNOLOGY for the **complete biodigestion** and transformation of pollutant molecules into inert elements in the food chain and natural cycles.

By definition, the pollutant load of a wastewater is all additional elements that were introduced into the natural water. When the element is organic, its determination is given by identifying the concentration of carbon atoms in the mixture. The presence of organic carbon can be determined by the measurement of the Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD), indirectly, or by the concentration of Total Organic Carbon (TOC). The relationship between the two measurements, for domestic wastewater, is given by the following equation:

$$BOD_5 = 1,87 * TOC - 17$$

The different presentations of the organic carbon atom with its great capacity to generate highly soluble and homogeneous molecules in aqueous solution determine the complexity of a treatment system design.

Removing organic carbon from wastewater is one of the biggest goals of wastewater treatment

NVBS® bioreactors specifically consider in their modeling the **metabolic processes** that living organisms use from carbon sources. Its stoichiometric calculation considers attributions of the phases of bacterial growth that require bacterial cellular respiration and microbiological reproduction. For cellular respiration through utilization, if there is the presence of oxygen molecules (O₂) in the medium, the metabolic pathway uses the glucose molecule (C₆H₁₂O₆) through glycolysis in the Krebs cycle, which in condensed form can be explained by the following equation:

On the other hand, Darwin² already postulated within his theory of natural selection that **reproductive success** determines the capacity for evolution, a notorious fact in aerobic bacterial microbiology that uses this function in a highly efficient way and has made biological wastewater treatment the primary option for selecting the treatment method. While it is true that the carbon atom is not always molecularly configured as glucose, any element containing carbon is feasible for use by evolved aerobic microorganisms within the process of breaking chemical bonds and producing carbon dioxide or energy.

Extrapolating the pollutant load, i.e. the carbon to be removed based on microbial metabolic activity into the glycolysis equation, is the bottleneck of the technique to determine the exact molecular oxygen requirement that microorganisms need. **These complex variables and analytical determinations that are involved in the identification and control process have delayed the biological treatment of the production of organic sludge, the result of another bacterial process, known as chemotaxis.**

² Darwin, Charles - On the Origin of Species by Means of Natural Selection, or the Preservation of Favoured Races in the Struggle for Life. 6 ed. 1861

Chemotaxis is NOT A METABOLIC PATHWAY and is what aerobic biological wastewater treatment systems attempt to replicate. This activity allows the bacterium to detect the concentrations of chemical substances around it and generate a locomotion response through the production of proteins that protrude from its cell membrane, certain flagella. These flagella bind together the chemicals detected in the network of organic biomass, composed of polluting molecules and bacteria, in the form of sludge. At the same time, this sludge can, in a conventional way and simple physical actions of settling and sedimentation, facilitate it to be separated from the water and directed to another process.

Chemotaxis requires extensive knowledge of the concentrations of reagents (contaminants) in wastewater for the bacterial response to be efficient.

Clearly establishing the difference between a conventional aerobic biological process, which uses chemotaxis for sludge production; and the metabolic process of NVBS® bioreactors, which makes the complete biodigestion of molecular organic carbon through glycolysis, we show how our modeling is unique and gives the project an innovative vision.

In addition, **the NVBS® System** understands that introducing air into wastewater simply does not result in the availability of oxygen for the bacterial glycolysis reaction. In optimal conditions and clean water, i.e. only H₂O molecules, the average saturation is given with 8mg of oxygen in 1 liter of water. Any additional mass of oxygen does not mix with the water, and because the density of air is much lower than that of a fluid, the air creates an upward motion in the form of bubbles.

The presence of nutrients and/or life in the water constantly modifies the concentrations of available oxygen. Chemical elements can oxidize based on the presence of oxygen atoms, reducing their concentration, just as organisms will seek to use oxygen for their vital evolutionary functions.

The modeling of **the NVBS System** considers **physicochemical and biological properties that allow the control of oxygen to be controlled in the biological reactions within a fluid, but are not limited to the following physicochemical considerations®**, among others:

- Oxygen Bioavailability
- Graham's Law on Gas Diffusion (Lagoon Diffusion)
- Density of the medium
- Hydrostatic and hydrodynamic pressure of pollutant particles
- Solids Dynamics
- Archimedes' displacement theorem

Through the use of applied physics, total control of fluid velocities (liquids and gases) is created, the NVBS System achieves the maintenance of solids concentration through density stratification, identification of biochemical processes, and separation of bacterial variables into specific biotic niches®.

Fig. Biotic Niches on NVBS® Bioreactor

The modelling of the technology looks at the direct and indirect mechanisms in which the physicochemical characteristics of the solution are found, such as oxygen or CO₂ concentration, pH, pressure, nutrient concentration, inhibitory agents, competition; and the growth dynamics of each of the microorganism species in a microbial consortium are simulated.

The NVBS® bioreactor provides a highly specialized growing environment with species heterogeneity in homogeneous niches. Homogeneity within an individual biotic niche results in a limited ecological niche that tends to be often dominated by two to four species only, eliminating bacterial competition from conventional reactors.

The process operates in continuous flow mode, the advantage of which derived from the operation is that it results in the continuous selection of those microorganisms that are able to grow most efficiently in the stratified niches of the bioreactor. The most efficient growers will be subject to less cell washing in a specific niche and will therefore dominate the microbial population and consequently metabolism in this area.

The NVBS® bioreactor provides a large number of very different environments that support a great diversity of microorganisms. In addition, the process line contemplates the timing of when environments change as the stack ages and molecules shrink. The development of a microbiological consortium provides sufficient microbial diversity throughout the life of the reactor to ensure optimal performance.

All these features, together with the unique architecture that provides up to 90% smaller systems without sewage sludge production. The multiplicity of designs in a decentralized way observes the possibilities of population growth and respects investment expenditure in a staggered manner.

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